

Cobots in SMEs: Implementation Processes, Challenges, and Success Factors

Philipp Jennes
Institute of Management and EMBEDS Department
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies
Pisa, Italy
philipp.jennes@santannapisa.it

Alberto Di Minin
Institute of Management and EMBEDS Department
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies
Pisa, Italy
alberto.diminin@santannapisa.it

Abstract— The integration of industrial and collaborative robots (cobots) in Small and Medium Size Enterprises (SMEs) has been steadily growing. Cobots emerged as cost-effective, flexible, and lightweight industrial robots, which are easily tailored to the manufacturing needs of SMEs. Unfortunately, SMEs still encounter formidable challenges, while venturing into the realm of cobot integration. That is why this study seeks to investigate the processes, challenges, and success factors associated with the adoption of cobots in European manufacturing SMEs. We employed a qualitative exploratory case study methodology, incorporating interviews, observations, and document analysis. The findings reveal three primary clusters of barriers to cobot implementation: technical, organizational, and cultural. Technical challenges include complexities in programming and safety assessment, while organizational hurdles encompass job redesign and integration knowledge. Cultural barriers involve concerns such as the fear of job displacement, safety issues, and skepticism. Addressing these barriers is imperative for the successful implementation of cobots. These insights offer practical guidance to SMEs aiming to seamlessly integrate cobots and contribute to the existing literature on cobot implementation within SMEs. Furthermore, this research serves as a valuable resource for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers, aiding them in devising effective strategies for cobot adoption. By doing so, it promotes innovation and enhances competitiveness within the manufacturing sector.

Keywords—collaborative robots, cobots, adoption, implementation, industry 4.0, innovation, SMEs, manufacturing

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the integration of industrial and collaborative robots has exhibited significant growth, with a remarkable doubling in the past six years [1]. Traditional industrial robots, known for their speed and precision, do come with certain drawbacks, notably high costs and the need for substantial guarding and peripheral safety measures, limiting their adaptability. While these characteristics find utility in large corporations, smaller manufacturing enterprises require more cost-effective, agile solutions. Collaborative robots, often referred to as cobots, have emerged as a promising alternative [2]. Cobots are designed to work alongside human operators in a shared workspace, harnessing the combined strengths of machines and unique human skills. They boast attributes like lightweight construction, improved kinematics, and user-friendly programmable interfaces, all aimed at enhancing

user satisfaction, health, safety, and overall performance [3]. These attributes make cobots particularly suitable for dynamic production environments found in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), where product flow can change rapidly [4]. Consequently, experts identify significant market potential for cobots. Despite this potential, the concept of industrial Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) is relatively new, with limited research and still in its early stages of practical implementation [3]. To shed light on the implementation process, the challenges faced, and the key factors influencing the adoption of cobots, our study seeks to address the research question: *"What are the key implementation challenges, success factors, and the overall adoption process of cobots in manufacturing SMEs?"* In our study, we use a qualitative case study approach, conducting semi-structured interviews, observations, and document analysis to understand how European manufacturing SMEs adopt cobots. Our research endeavors to offer insights into the challenges associated with cobot adoption and to enhance our understanding of the functionality, usability, and environmental conditions necessary for the successful implementation of cobots [5].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Cobot Interaction and Safety Standards

To gain a comprehensive understanding of cobots, examining their interactions with human workers is essential. Utilizing The International Federation of Robotics' classification, which delineates four distinct collaboration types between robots and human workers [6] offers a clearer conceptualization, as presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: TYPES OF COLLABORATION IN HUMAN-ROBOT INTERACTION

Type of Collaboration	Description
Coexistent Collaboration	Humans and robots work together in a shared space without physical barriers, ensuring optimal safety.
Sequential Collaboration	Humans and robots synchronize their tasks in a shared workspace, with only one partner active at a time.
Cooperative Collaboration	Humans and robots operate concurrently in the same workspace but not on the same task.
Responsive Collaboration	Robots react to human movements in real-time during tasks, emphasizing sensor technology, worker safety, and security standards.

Effectively implementing cyber-physical systems in collaborative environments necessitates a strong focus on security. The European conformity assessment of machinery

encompasses three key areas: Type A, providing universal safety guidance (e.g., ISO 12100); Type B, addressing specific safety aspects; and Type C, identifying risks tied to specific machine types, exemplified by the ISO 10218 family for industrial robots. With the proliferation of commercially available cobots, the ISO/TS 15066:2016 has been introduced as an adjunct to ISO 10218. This specification outlines safety requirements for collaborative industrial robot systems, with a particular emphasis on their work environment, in addition to providing operational guidance [6].

B. Common Applications of Cobots

Cobots find extensive applications in various industries, offering versatility and multifunctionality. Key tasks associated with cobots include: Assembly, Pick and Place, Machine Tending, Quality Inspection, and Palletizing. The adaptability and multifunctionality of cobots make them invaluable assets for streamlining operations, boosting productivity, and promoting a safer working environment [7].

C. The Heterogeneity of SMEs

SMEs hold a crucial position within diverse economies, showcasing their extensive presence across various industries and contexts [8]. The classification of SMEs varies significantly, with countries adopting distinct criteria. For instance, in the European Union, SMEs are typically characterized as companies with up to 250 employees, while the United States extends the threshold to 1500 employees. Furthermore, the financial scale of SMEs exhibits variations, with values ranging from below 1 million EUR in the USA to less than 280 million EUR for high-tech SMEs in China. Therefore, comprehending and differentiating different types of SMEs becomes indispensable for targeted policies, efficient allocation of resources, sector-specific strategies, market comprehension, and comparative analysis [9]. Within our research, we utilize the categorization framework put forth by [9] to effectively differentiate and categorize diverse SMEs. According to their classification, SMEs within the European Union encompass a substantial portion, comprising approximately 90% of the economy. These entities play a significant role in job creation, contributing approximately 60% to the overall employment landscape. Furthermore, SMEs are characterized as firms employing a maximum of 250 individuals with an annual revenue not exceeding 50 million EUR or an annual balance sheet total of 43 million EUR or less.

D. Technology Adoption Challenges faced by SMEs

The advent of technological innovation has brought about substantial transformations in the performance of businesses, particularly within SMEs [10]. The implementation of novel, adaptable, and flexible manufacturing solutions within SMEs enables the simultaneous production of diverse products, enhances machine utilization, minimizes in-process inventory levels, and reduces response time [11]–[13]. These measures are crucial for catering to customer preferences, thereby enhancing customer satisfaction and maintaining a competitive edge in the market [14]. Despite the potential benefits that automation holds for manufacturing SMEs, the implementation of automation technologies poses common challenges related to technology adoption [15]. These challenges encompass the lack of technical skills and

efficiency, the cost of technology and infrastructure, limited organizational support, the absence of adequate governmental support, and attitude challenges of the employees.

E. Open Innovation in Manufacturing SMEs

Open innovation is a concept that emphasizes collaboration and the purposeful sharing of knowledge and ideas between organizations, individuals, and external partners [16]–[18]. It challenges the traditional closed innovation model, where companies primarily rely on internal research and development (R&D) to drive innovation. In contrast, open innovation recognizes the value of external inputs and seeks to leverage external expertise, resources, and networks to enhance innovation capabilities [16]. For manufacturing SMEs, open innovation offers several important benefits. Firstly, it allows SMEs to overcome resource constraints by accessing external knowledge, technology, and funding, which is particularly valuable considering their limited R&D budgets and expertise [19]. Moreover, SMEs are well-suited for embracing open innovation due to their inherent characteristics, including flexibility, agile decision-making processes, and responsiveness [9], [20]. These attributes enable SMEs to swiftly adapt their strategic directions and effectively leverage the benefits of open innovation [9], [21]. Furthermore, facilitating knowledge transfer across organizational boundaries significantly influences innovation performance within open innovation initiatives [22], [23]. In contrast to established enterprises, SMEs exhibit a higher degree of agility, enabling them to promptly adapt, reshape their business models, and contribute to the ecosystem of business [15], [24]. This agile approach aligns with the positive correlation observed between the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies and the implementation of open innovation practices by SMEs, emphasizing the importance of embracing technological advancements and external knowledge to drive innovation within the SME sector [25].

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative approach, specifically a case study design [26]. This approach involves inductive research, focusing on comprehensive data examination to derive concepts, themes, or models directly from the data itself [27]. The study investigates five manufacturing SMEs, each representing different company sizes, nationalities, and industries, such as metal and machining, glass manufacturing, precision mechanics, plastics, and printing. The diverse selection of SMEs provides comprehensive insights into cobot integration within various organizational contexts. The case study design allows for in-depth exploration of experiences, challenges, and outcomes related to cobot implementation across these settings [28], [29].

A. Case Study

This study specifically examines SMEs that have successfully integrated at least one cobot into their manufacturing processes. Details of these case SMEs are provided in Table 2.

TABLE 2: SAMPLE CASE STUDY PARTICIPANTS

SME Reference	Interviewee position	Size	Industry	Task
A	CEO	7 (micro)	Metal and machining	Machine tending
B	CEO	28 (small)	Glas manufacturing	Machine tending
C	Development Engineer	120 (medium)	Precision mechanics	Machine tending
D	CEO	100 (medium)	Plastics industry	Pick and place
E	CEO	227 (medium)	Printing Industry	Pick and place

B. Data Analysis

Qualitative data collection involved semi-structured interviews with key decision-makers responsible for cobot acquisition and integration in SMEs located in Italy, Finland, and Germany. An inductive approach was used during the analysis, with open-ended questions to identify implementation challenges and success factors. Patterns and clusters emerged from the data, forming the basis for generalizations or theories [26].

IV. CHALLENGES

A. Technical Barriers

a) Programming Complexity: Programming cobots is vital for their effective operation and maintenance, demanding adaptability and continuous learning due to varying industry skill requirements. SME B's CEO revealed persistent challenges: *"I still have to do all the programs myself with the machines."* SME A emphasized the importance of programming skills for modifying cobot motions. SME C highlighted the complexity of program changes, a significant implementation barrier. Moreover, SME D noted that troubleshooting demands more knowledge and training. Our findings confirm that programming complexity remains a challenge in cobot operations and troubleshooting for operators and integrators alike.

b) Safety assessment: Safety assessment in the domain of HRC is a fundamental requirement due to the close proximity between humans and robots, coupled with the unpredictable nature of human behavior [30]. While the ISO/TS 15066:2016 specifies safety requirements for collaborative industrial robot systems, it supplements Type C standards by offering additional guidance for risk assessments. However, our interviews revealed that these guidelines are often perceived as somewhat ambiguous in terms of the concrete actions and measures required. For instance, the CEO of SME A described the existing guidelines as being *"a little bit in a grey area"*, and the integrator of SME C remarked that *"there is not a strict line on what has to be done for the risk assessment."* This finding aligns with the outcomes of a case study by [4], highlighting the need for more precise guidelines in the field. This demand for clarity has prompted the exploration of more intuitive safety assessment approaches. In our study, two SMEs adopted observational methods to assess safety, quantify risks, and subsequently improve safety measures based on post-implementation incidents. This underscores the urgent requirement for clearer and more comprehensive guidelines that provide actionable steps for risk mitigation.

B. Organizational Barriers

a) Integration Knowledge:

The effective implementation of cobots in manufacturing environments is contingent on the acquisition and application of integration knowledge, a topic extensively discussed in our interviews. The lack of expertise in this domain significantly hampers the seamless integration of cobots into existing production lines [31]. Insights from SMEs interviewed during the study elucidate the challenges linked to integration knowledge. For instance, SME B's CEO conveyed the initial challenges encountered upon cobot acquisition: *"I was completely overwhelmed."* Due to the lack of standardized blueprints for quick process redesign, SME B further revealed the significant time investment required for building the necessary peripherals, taking approximately half a year. This highlights the complexity involved in integrating cobots into existing systems. SME A faced similar challenges and recognized the insufficiency of knowledge: *"In our case, the knowledge was not enough."* SME C's integrator stressed that the main challenge lies in reevaluating existing processes, not the cobot itself. The CEO of SME D similarly noted that a cobot is a tool requiring competencies in mechanics and electronics. Integration knowledge gaps have also been a critical impediment to technology adoption in SME B. Many managers are wary of implementing cobots as they perceive them as standalone machines. To address this, the CEO stressed the significance of government initiatives to provide training sessions in educational institutions. This proactive approach aims to develop future operators and alleviate concerns about working alongside cobots. The impending shortage of skilled workers further underscores the need to instill enthusiasm in young individuals and make working with cobots an appealing prospect.

b) Job Redesign: The implementation of cobots in work environments often requires a substantial overhaul of current job tasks and workflows, calling for the redefinition of traditional roles and responsibilities to facilitate optimized collaborative interaction between humans and robots. This process demands meticulous planning and careful consideration [32]. Employees may express concerns regarding the potential increase in their workload following the introduction of collaborative robots, contributing to resistance to change within the workforce. This arises from the perception that employees may be tasked with monitoring or maintaining the cobots alongside their existing responsibilities [33]. Our findings show that resistance to change was initialized by the fear of increased workload. The CEO of SME E expressed concerns about instructing employees to operate two machines, as it was perceived by the employees as an increased workload: *"(employee reconfiguration) was a little bit more of a problem, because the employees were instructed by us to operate two machines. From the employees' perspective, that meant twice the work."*

C. Cultural Barriers

a) Fear of job loss: Employees experiencing fear of job loss may resist the implementation of cobots as they worry about their job security and future career prospects. This fear can create a sense of uncertainty and anxiety within the worker, leading to a reluctance to accept cobots and the changes they bring [34]. Our findings indicate that

organizational resistance to change was evident as a result of concerns surrounding this phenomenon associated with automation.

b) *Fear of Safety*: The proximity between cobots and human operators facilitates the development of concerns regarding possible accidents or injuries, which can cause worries among employees. This is particularly true if they are unfamiliar with the technology or lack confidence in the safety measures implemented alongside cobots. This construct was evident in SME A in which the CEO expressed: *“There were people who were afraid of the cobot colliding with them.”*

c) *Skepticism*: In the realm of technology acceptance and adoption, skepticism assumes a pivotal role, encompassing doubts, reservations, and reluctance exhibited by individuals and organizations towards the adoption of novel technologies. Skepticism can originate from diverse sources, including fear of the unknown, apprehensions regarding technology effectiveness and reliability and a dearth of familiarity or comprehension [35]. According to integrator of SME C, employees harbored skepticism towards cobots prior to implementation, primarily due to a lack of communication: *“At the beginning, people were more skeptical.”*

V. SUCCESS FACTORS

A. Vision

Leaders with a clear vision of cobots' benefits and the ability to inspire their teams facilitate a positive innovation mindset that expedites implementation [36]. Our study participants recognized several benefits aligned with their goals, including:

- Utilizing skilled workers for more valuable tasks: *“We relocated the value that a person can add to where it's needed most.” (SME D CEO)*
- Enhancing performance and consistency: *“Delivery dates can be met, work consistency has increased.” (SME B CEO)*
- Improving safety by eliminating ergonomic issues: *“(Ergonomics) played a role, especially with repetitive tasks.” (SME C Integrator)*
- Achieving cost savings through compact automation: *“A versatile instrument at a low cost.” (SME B CEO)*
- Gaining competitive advantages with agile responsiveness and scalability: *“The competitive advantage is replicability.” (SME D CEO)*

Managers focusing on these benefits foster a shared understanding, mitigating resistance to change and cultivating a positive cultural mindset.

B. Open Innovation

The collaboration between various stakeholders emerged as highly advantageous for SMEs, particularly in addressing the lack of integration expertise. For instance, the CEO of SME B engaged in collaborative discussions with the distributor to enhance a program, while SME C's integrator participated in training sessions, webinars, and events organized by the distributor and external parties, leading to

valuable knowledge exchange and improvement opportunities: *“The manufacturer provides some training and I went through it in school as training (...) and then also all the web classes for basic and advanced training.”* By adopting this approach, the initially recognized challenges related to program complexity and integration expertise can be effectively addressed. As a result, open innovation fosters a culture of collaboration and ongoing learning, thereby significantly enhancing the implementation process.

C. Pilot Project

A pilot project, based on [37], involves testing cobots in a limited scope to assess their effectiveness and feasibility. It serves as a trial phase to gather data, evaluate performance, and address challenges before broader implementation. SME E successfully implemented this approach, installing the first cobot 1.5 months before the second one. The gradual implementation allowed employees to acclimate, realizing the benefits: *“We installed the first cobot 1.5 months before the second one (...) employees got used to it (...) it worked very well (...) has become standard in our company.”* This approach enables the study of workforce behavior before expansion.

D. Open Communication

Open communication is a fundamental change management strategy in cobot implementation, addressing concerns and enhancing awareness, thereby facilitating successful integration [38]. In SME D, fear of job loss was mitigated by sharing information about cobot investment, portraying them as enhancers of human capabilities: *“When employees and managers saw the information on automation investment and its swift implementation, those dedicated to their jobs were pleased. We successfully portrayed cobots as assistants to our workforce.”* Similarly, SME A alleviated safety concerns by involving workers in discussions and allowing them to observe cobot movements. This hands-on approach built trust and confidence among the workforce.

E. Employee Involvement

Another effective change management strategy that fosters technology adoption is the involvement of employees. Involving employees throughout the integration process can be done by providing sufficient training opportunities and engaging them in decision-making processes. SME B, SME C, SME D and SME E exemplify this approach by providing adequate training sessions for operators, ensuring they are well-prepared to handle the responsibilities associated with cobot integration. SME C additionally followed the approach to integrate the workers into the decision-making process by engaging them into an open dialog about the benefits and concerns of cobots and thus mitigating organizational skepticism. Through employee involvement, organizations harness the expertise and experience of their workforce, leading to smoother transitions and improved collaboration.

VI. DISCUSSION

Our examination of the obstacles faced in the implementation of cobots has unveiled three primary clusters: technical barriers, organizational barriers, and cultural barriers. It is important to recognize that our findings are based on a relatively small sample size. As such, the

generalizability of the results to all SMEs may be limited. While we acknowledge this constraint, we believe that the depth and richness of the insights gained from our case studies offer meaningful contributions to the scholarly discourse surrounding technology adoption in SMEs. The challenges identified in this study largely align with the prevailing challenges encountered by SMEs. Firstly, insufficient technical skills and inefficiency pose significant obstacles to the successful adoption of technology for employees, managers, and owners. This challenge restricts the capacity of individuals to efficiently integrate and harness technological advancements [15]. Notably, we emphasize the importance of integration knowledge, programming complexity, and risk assessments in highlighting the existing expertise gap, which calls for necessary actions to enable the smooth adoption of cobots. Secondly, attitude behavior is recognized as a common challenge in technology adoption [39]. Our study contributes to this aspect by providing in-depth insights into the cultural barriers faced by employees, including skepticism, fear of job loss, and safety concerns. Thirdly, lack of organizational support has emerged as a significant adoption barrier for Industry 4.0 technologies in SMEs, as indicated by previous research [15]. This barrier encompasses various challenges and limitations arising from insufficient support within the organizational structure. Factors such as limited organizational readiness and the absence of a clear implementation strategy contribute to this barrier. Our study findings align with this result, as they shed light on the experiences of managers who encountered difficulties in defining suitable cobot solutions for their production facilities beforehand, and on potential difficulties that can arise when employees are not adequately rescheduled within their existing work environments. This further stresses the importance of integration knowledge and effective leadership. Moreover, inadequate government support has emerged as a significant impediment to technology adoption among SMEs [39]. In line with this result, our study reinforces the significance of governmental initiatives, as highlighted by our interviewees, who emphasized the necessity of training and education programs. Finally, contrasting existing literature, our research results challenge the notion that limited financial resources act as a barrier to the integration of cobots. Prior studies have consistently highlighted the cost factor as a prominent barrier to the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies [15], [39], [40]. Scholars have emphasized that SMEs often face difficulties in securing the necessary funds to cover the direct and indirect expenses associated with acquiring Industry 4.0 technologies. However, our experts have indicated a different perspective, suggesting that the cost factor is not a major barrier but, rather, a potential benefit. They emphasized favorable financial benefits of cobots over industrial robots or human workers. Notwithstanding the challenges encountered by the participants in our case study, the selected SMEs in our research successfully implemented cobots. Therefore, a vital focus of our study was to identify the key success factors that facilitated the mitigation of the aforementioned challenges. Firstly, having a clear vision regarding the advantages and potential of cobots played an important role in inspiring a positive attitude towards innovation among the stakeholders. Secondly, adopting an

open innovation approach proved to be effective in addressing challenges related to programming complexity and integration expertise. By actively involving external partners and stakeholders, SMEs successfully engaged in knowledge sharing with their distributors, harnessed valuable expertise, and effectively overcame technical barriers. These findings underscore SMEs' inherent traits, marked by agility and flexible decision-making, enabling the integration of open innovation practices [9]. Moreover, using a pilot project proved valuable for cobot implementation. It allowed testing, data gathering, performance evaluation, and assessment of human perceptions before scaling up. Furthermore, open communication addressed concerns during implementation. It facilitated information sharing about cobots, their benefits, and their impact, mitigating resistance. Finally, employee involvement was crucial, empowering them through training and decision-making.

VII. IMPLICATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

Integrating cobots enhances SME competitiveness, but implementation challenges are common [11], [29]. This exploratory case study delved into the adoption processes of cobots by examining five diverse manufacturing SMEs from various sectors and national backgrounds. The findings presented here offer valuable insights into cobot implementation, contributing to existing literature. These insights help SMEs understand critical factors for successful integration and guide future implementation. Managers can use these findings to develop effective strategies, considering SME-specific challenges. Policymakers can leverage this understanding to design initiatives that promote cobot adoption, fostering SME growth and advancing the manufacturing sector. This study provides cobot implementation insights but has limitations and suggests future research directions. Firstly, the study focused on successful SMEs, potentially introducing bias. Future research should include SMEs that faced difficulties or failure in cobot integration. Secondly, the study included a limited sample from specific countries. Caution should be exercised when applying the results to a wider context. Future research should include a larger, more diverse sample of SMEs. Finally, future research should explore open innovation practices and open business models to enhance value creation and cobot adoption within manufacturing ecosystems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to Professor Agnieszka Radziwon for her invaluable assistance and significant contributions to the development of this paper. Her expertise, guidance, and insightful feedback were instrumental in shaping the research and improving the quality of this work. This research has received funding from the EU's Horizon2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 956745, EINST4INE: The European Training Network for Industry Digital Transformation across Innovation Ecosystems. The content of this publication does not reflect the official opinion of the EU. Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the publication lies entirely with the authors.

REFERENCES

- [1] IFR, "World Robotics: Industrial Robots 2022," p. 52, 2022, [Online]. Available: https://ifr.org/downloads/press2018/2022_WR_extended_version.pdf.
- [2] L. Da Xu, E. L. Xu, and L. Li, "Industry 4.0: State of the art and future trends," *Int. J. Prod. Res.*, vol. 56, no. 8, pp. 2941–2962, 2018, doi: 10.1080/00207543.2018.1444806.
- [3] T. Kopp, M. Baumgartner, and S. Kinkel, "Success factors for introducing industrial human-robot interaction in practice: an empirically driven framework," *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.*, pp. 685–704, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s00170-020-06398-0.
- [4] M. Schnell and M. Holm, "Challenges for Manufacturing SMEs in the Introduction of Collaborative Robots," *Adv. Transdiscipl. Eng.*, vol. 21, pp. 173–183, 2022, doi: 10.3233/ATDE220137.
- [5] T. Kopp, A. Schäfer, and S. Kinkel, "Kollaborierende oder kollaborationsfähige Roboter in der Praxis," *Fabriksoftware*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 52–58, 2021, doi: 10.30844/I40M.
- [6] L. Caruana and E. Francalanza, "Safety 4.0 for Collaborative Robotics in the Factories of the Future," *FME Trans.*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 842–850, 2021, doi: 10.5937/FME2104842C.
- [7] A. A. Malik and A. Bilberg, "Collaborative robots in assembly: A practical approach for tasks distribution," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 81, no. March, pp. 665–670, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.procir.2019.03.173.
- [8] X. Lecocq and B. Demil, "Strategizing industry structure: The case of open systems in a low-tech industry," *Strateg. Manag. J.*, vol. 27, no. 9, pp. 891–898, 2006, doi: 10.1002/smj.544.
- [9] A. Radziwon and W. Vanhaverbeke, "Open innovation in small and medium-sized enterprises," in *The Oxford handbook of open innovation*, H. Chesbrough, A. Radziwon, W. Vanhaverbeke, and J. West, Eds. Oxford University Press, 2023, ch. 8, pp. 119–139.
- [10] M. M. H. Shahadat, M. Nekmahmud, P. Ebrahimi, and M. Fekete-Farkas, "Digital Technology Adoption in SMEs: What Technological, Environmental and Organizational Factors Influence SMEs' ICT Adoption in Emerging Countries?," *Glob. Bus. Rev.*, no. February, 2023, doi: 10.1177/09721509221137199.
- [11] A. Radziwon, H. Blichfeldt, A. Bilberg, E. S. Madsen, and M. Bogers, "Exploring manufacturing solutions for SMEs," *21st EurOMA*, pp. 1–10, 2014.
- [12] C. Eroglu and C. Hofer, "Lean, leaner, too lean? the inventory-performance link revisited," *J. Oper. Manag.*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 356–369, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.jom.2010.05.002.
- [13] H. A. El Maraghy, "Flexible and reconfigurable manufacturing systems paradigms," *Flex. Serv. Manuf. J.*, vol. 17, no. 4 SPECIAL ISSUE, pp. 261–276, 2006, doi: 10.1007/s10696-006-9028-7.
- [14] J. Aitken, M. Christopher, and D. Towill, "Understanding, Implementing and Exploiting Agility and Leanness," *Int. J. Logist. Res. Appl.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 59–74, 2002, doi: 10.1080/13675560110084139.
- [15] A. A. Shaikh, A. Kumar, A. A. Syed and M.Z. Shaikh, "A Two-Decade Literature Review on Challenges Faced By Smes in Technology Adoption" *Acad. Mark. Stud. J.*, vol. 25, no. April, pp. 1–14, 2021, [Online]. Available: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3823849.
- [16] H. Chesbrough, "Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology," *Jan.* 2003.
- [17] M. Bogers et al., "The open innovation research landscape: established perspectives and emerging themes across different levels of analysis," *Ind. Innov.*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 8–40, 2017, doi: 10.1080/13662716.2016.1240068.
- [18] A. Radziwon and H. Chesbrough, "Open innovation as a field of knowledge," in *The Oxford handbook of open innovation*, H. Chesbrough, A. Radziwon, W. Vanhaverbeke, and J. West, Eds. Oxford University Press, 2023, ch. 2, pp. 19–36.
- [19] S. Brunswicker and W. Vanhaverbeke, "Open Innovation in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs): External Knowledge Sourcing Strategies and Internal Organizational Facilitators," *J. Small Bus. Manag.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1241–1263, 2015, doi: 10.1111/jsbm.12120.
- [20] J. Mitra, *The Business of Innovation*. 2017.
- [21] R. Narula, "R&D collaboration by SMEs: New opportunities and limitations in the face of globalisation," *Technovation*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 153–161, 2004, doi: 10.1016/S0166-4972(02)00045-7.
- [22] V. Parida, M. Westerberg, and J. Frishammar, "Inbound Open Innovation Activities in High - Tech SMEs: The Impact on Innovation Performance," *J. Small Bus. Manag. - J SMALL BUS Manag.*, vol. 50, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1111/j.1540-627X.2012.00354.x.
- [23] A. Radziwon and M. Bogers, "Managing SMEs' collaboration across organizational boundaries within a regional business ecosystem," no. February. 2018.
- [24] A. Radziwon, M. Bogers, and A. Bilberg, "Creating and capturing value in a regional innovation ecosystem: A study of how manufacturing SMEs develop collaborative solutions," *Int. J. Technol. Manag.*, vol. 75, no. 1–4, pp. 73–96, 2017, doi: 10.1504/IJTM.2017.085694.
- [25] A. Messeni Petruzzelli, G. Murgia, and A. Parmentola, "How can open innovation support SMEs in the adoption of I4.0 technologies? An empirical analysis," *R D Manag.*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 615–632, 2022, doi: 10.1111/radm.12507.
- [26] M. Ishtiaq, "Book Review Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage," *English Lang. Teach.*, vol. 12, p. 40, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.5539/elt.v12n5p40.
- [27] D. R. Thomas, "A General Inductive Approach for Analyzing Qualitative Evaluation Data," *Am. J. Eval.*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 237–246, 2006, doi: 10.1177/1098214005283748.
- [28] T. Aberdeen, "Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods* (4th Ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage," *Can. J. Action Res.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 69–71, 2013, doi: 10.33524/cjar.v14i1.73.
- [29] B. A. Kadir, O. Broberg, and C. Souza Da Conceição, "Designing human-robot collaborations in industry 4.0: Explorative case studies," *Proc. Int. Des. Conf. Des.*, vol. 2, pp. 601–610, 2018, doi: 10.21278/idc.2018.0319.
- [30] M. Askarpour, L. Lestingi, F. Buran, M. Rossi, and F. Vicentini, "Model-driven Risk Analysis for the Design of Safe Collaborative Robotic Applications," *Proc. 2020 IEEE Int. Conf. Human-Machine Syst. ICHMS 2020*, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ICHMS49158.2020.9209450.
- [31] I. Aaltonen and T. Salmi, "Experiences and expectations of collaborative robots in industry and academia: Barriers and development needs," *Procedia Manuf.*, vol. 38, no. 2019, pp. 1151–1158, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.promfg.2020.01.204.
- [32] J. Wallace, "Getting collaborative robots to work: A study of ethics emerging during the implementation of cobots," *Paladyn*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 299–309, 2021, doi: 10.1515/pjbr-2021-0019.
- [33] C. Apostolidis, A. Devine, and A. Jabbar, "From chalk to clicks – The impact of (rapid) technology adoption on employee emotions in the higher education sector," *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change*, vol. 182, no. June, p. 121860, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121860.
- [34] W. Lambrechts, J. S. Klaver, L. Koudijzer, and J. Semeijn, "Human Factors Influencing the Implementation of Cobots in High Volume Distribution Centres," *Logistics*, vol. 5, no. 2, 2021, doi: 10.3390/logistics5020032.
- [35] L. Ni, W. Liu, Y. Huang, and M. Pan, "Technology Adoption and Promotion in the Age of Skepticism: Examining COVID-19 Mitigation through Technological and Human Factors," *J. Promot. Manag.*, pp. 1–22, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1080/10496491.2023.2165207.
- [36] C. Luzinski, "Transformational leadership," *J. Nurs. Adm.*, vol. 41, no. 12, pp. 501–502, 2011, doi: 10.1097/NNA.0b013e3182378a71.
- [37] R. ter Huurne, L. O. Scholtenhuis, and A. Dorée, "Change Triggers in Early Innovation Stages: How Technology Pilots Enable Routine Reflection," *J. Constr. Eng. Manag.*, vol. 148, no. 9, pp. 1–10, 2022, doi: 10.1061/(asce)co.1943-7862.0002307.
- [38] C. I. Maican, A. M. Cazan, R. C. Lixandroui, and L. Dovleac, "A study on academic staff personality and technology acceptance: The case of communication and collaboration applications," *Comput. Educ.*, vol. 128, pp. 113–131, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2018.09.010.
- [39] M. Ghobakhloo, M. Iranmanesh, M. Vilkas, A. Grybauskas, and A. Amran, "Drivers and barriers of Industry 4.0 technology adoption among manufacturing SMEs: a systematic review and transformation roadmap," *J. Manuf. Technol. Manag.*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 1029–1058, 2022, doi: 10.1108/JMTM-12-2021-0505.
- [40] S. Coleman, R. Göb, G. Manco, A. Pievatolo, X. Tort-Martorell, and M. S. Reis, "How Can SMEs Benefit from Big Data? Challenges and a Path Forward," *Qual. Reliab. Eng. Int.*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 2151–2164, 2016, doi: 10.1002/qre.2008.